

The Formation and Stability of Polybromide Derivatives of Heterocyclic Compounds. Part I. The Bromination of Diphenyl- ψ -thiohydantoin and its *ortho*-Tolyl Homologue.

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It has been shown that treatment of a solution of benzthiazole in chloroform at low temperatures with a molecular proportion of bromine gives rise to a dibromide (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 125), whose properties suggest that the bromine atoms are held to the nuclear nitrogen atom by means of semipolar single bonds, after the manner of attachment of the labile chlorine atoms to the phosphorus atom in phosphorus pentachloride (Prideaux, *Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 42, 672; Ingold and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1315; Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1176). A similar series of dibromo-addition compounds have also been obtained from the 5-chloro-3-bromo-1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles (Dyson, Hunter, Jones, and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 147), which are characterised by their extraordinary thermal stability to temperatures within 20° or so of their melting points, at which rapid decomposition sets in without any indication of an equilibrium of the type which has been observed by Ephraim in the case of alkali perhalides (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1069). In the presence of a large excess of the halogen, however, benzthiazole yields a highly unstable tetrabromide, analogous to the more stable tetrabromide of 1-phenylbenzthiazole (Bogert and Abrahamson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 826; Hunter, *loc. cit.*). The formation of these compounds by a repetition of the process of singlet sharing, leading to the production of the $\equiv \text{N} \begin{matrix} \cdot\text{Br} \\ \cdot\text{Br} \\ \cdot\text{Br} \end{matrix}$ complex is not difficult to visualise.

Now it is clear that if this interpretation of the mechanism of formation of these compounds is correct, the phenomenon must permeate, in greater or lesser degree, the whole field of heterocyclic compounds in which hetero atoms containing lone pairs of unshared electrons are encountered. It is therefore the object of this series of investigations, to study the behaviour of different heterocyclic systems towards bromine, and to examine the effect of substituents on the formation and stability of their bromo-addition compounds in relation to their suggested electronic constitution.

Particular interest attaches itself to the compounds of sulphur and nitrogen in view of the apparent expansion of the valency group of sulphur to twelve electrons in sulphur hexafluoride, and it has already been shown that the nuclear sulphur atom of the benzthiazole system exhibits the characteristic inertness of that in thiophen (Hunter, *loc. cit.*). This has been interpreted on the basis of the sextuple group theory of aromatic stability (Armit and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1605; Goss and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 1268), which receives further support from Hückel's recent wave mechanical analysis of the benzene molecule (*Z. Physik*, 1931, 70, 204). This author has had to make a number of assumptions which may or may not be entirely justifiable, but he has shown that by working out the quantum states of the six electrons over and above those required for joining carbon to carbon and carbon to hydrogen, and applying Pauli's principle, that a system of six electrons constitutes a "closed group" somewhat analogous to the closed groups of the Periodic system. Although the effect of disturbed symmetry in heterocyclic compounds such as pyridine, thiophen, and thiazole which exhibit aromatic characteristics cannot be calculated, it is clearly reasonable to assume that the importance of the sextuple group still persists in relation to their chemical behaviour.

It therefore appeared of interest to examine the reactivity of the reduced thiazole nucleus towards bromine, and the ψ -thiohydantoin were selected for this purpose.

The bromination of diphenyl- ψ -thiohydantoin (I), in chloroform at low temperatures, gave rise to a well defined vermilion compound, possessing the composition of a hexabromide of the tetrahydrothiazole. Only two thirds of its total bromine was, however, labile towards potassium iodide and on reduction with sulphurous acid it yielded 2-phenyl-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole (II), whose constitution follows from its synthesis from *p*-bromo-*s*-diphenylthiocarbamide and monochloroacetic acid (Dains, Irvin, and Harrel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 613).

These reactions clearly exclude the possibility of addition of bromine to the double bond of the 2-phenylimino grouping in the original ψ -thiohydantoin, and the bromo-addition compound is evidently a *hydropentabromide* of the bromophenyltetrahydrothiazole (II), which is confirmed by its synthesis from the bromophenyltetrahydrothiazole, hydrogen bromide, and bromine.

There is clearly a choice of formulae (III) and (IV) for the hydropentabromide, depending on whether the sulphur atom of the ψ -thiohydantoin complex is reactive as in the dialkyl sulphides (Cahours, *Annalen*, 1865, 135, 355), or inert as in thiophen and benzthiazole.

The sulphonium bromide formula (IV) is, however, excluded by the fact that the hydropentabromide yields 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole, and *not* the sulfoxide (V) on treatment with precipitated mercuric oxide.

On exposure to the atmosphere, or on keeping in a desiccator over potassium hydroxide, the hydropentabromide lost bromine yielding a stable yellow *hydrotribromide* of 2-phenyl-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole. This compound was also obtained by thermal decomposition of the hydropentabromide, under reduced pressure at a temperature some 25° below its melting point, when dissociation took place in accordance with the equation:

The bromination of 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole in chloroform at low temperatures, yielded an unstable *octabromide*, which regenerated the original ψ -thiohydantoin (II) on treatment with sulphurous acid. On the other hand, its labile bromine content as determined by iodometric titration in chloroform, indicated the presence of only six labile bromine atoms.

It has been shown that this loss is due to nuclear substitution under the conditions of the reaction, leading to the production of a dibromo substitution derivative of diphenyl- ψ -thiohydantoin, which is different from 2-*p*-bromophenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole (VI) which was synthesised from *s*-di-*p*-bromophenylthiocarbamide and monochloroacetic acid (Dains, Irvin, and Harrel, *loc. cit.*), and which is evidently the 2-phenylimino-3-*o*-*p*-dibromophenyl derivative (VII).

(VI)

(VII)

This difference in reactivity of labile bromine towards sulphurous acid and potassium iodide has already been observed in the case of the tetrabromide of 1-phenylbenzthiazole (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 138), and is evidently due to the fact that the second reaction is preceded by a hydrolysis of labile bromine to hypobromous acid, which then reacts with hydriodic acid in the usual way.

This receives confirmation from the fact that a solution of the octabromide in chloroform undergoes nuclear substitution with the production of the dibromo derivative, on being shaken with water.

The octabromide also regenerated the original 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole on treatment with mercuric oxide, indicating that the perbromide complexes are attached to nitrogen, and that in the ψ -thiohydantoin base as well as in the ammonium ion derived from it, the nuclear sulphur atom retains the characteristic inertness of the sulphur atom in thiazole and benzthiazole. This is of particular interest, since in this case there can be no question of the lone electrons of the sulphur atom being required for the formation of a sextuple group.

The bromination of di-*o*-tolyl- ψ -thiohydation (I, with $o\text{-C}_7\text{H}_7$ in place of Ph) at low temperatures, yielded an unstable *hydroheptabromide* of a monobromo-substitution derivative, which is almost certainly 2-*o*-tolylimino-3-*p*-bromo-*o*-tolyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole, although it has not yet been possible to isolate a synthetic specimen of this ψ -thiohydantoin from the condensation of *s*-*o*-tolyl-*p*-bromo-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide and monochloroacetic acid. On exposure to air, the hydroheptabromide lost bromine yielding a stable yellow *hydrotribromide*, similar to the compound obtained by degradation of the hypopentabromide of 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole (diphenyl- ψ -thiohydantoin) was prepared in 90 p.c. yield by heating a solution of thio-carbanilide (23 g.), monochloroacetic acid (9.5 g.) and pyridine (16 c.c.) in alcohol under reflux for 5-6 hours. It separated from alcoholethyl acetate in needles, m. p. 175° (compare Lange, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 596; Liebermann, *Annalen*, 1881, 207, 123).

2-Phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole *hypopentabromide*. (i) *Bromination of diphenyl- ψ -thiohydantoin*.—A solution of the hydantoin (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c. c.) was cooled to 0–3° and treated with bromine (0.8 c. c. in 0.8 c. c. of the same solvent), when the *hypopentabromide* crystallised after a minute or two. After being dried on porous earthenware, in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide for a short time, it formed glistening vermilion plates which become yellow with loss of bromine vapour at about 140° and had m. p. 161–63° (decomp. with effervescence). [Found: Br (total), 64.1, 64.0; Br (labile), 42.0, 41.6. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{BrS}$, HBr (Br_4) requires Br (total), 64.2; Br (labile), 42.8 per cent.]. On exposure to air for 24 hours, the hypopentabromide lost bromine yielding a stable yellow *hydrotribromide*, which after being digested for a few minutes with boiling chloroform in which it is almost insoluble, and drying in a vacuum, had m. p. 145–46° (decomp.). [Found: Br, 54.0. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}_2\text{BrS}$, HBr (Br_2) requires Br, 54.4 per cent.]. On treatment with sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide, both of these bromo-addition compounds yielded 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole, which separated from ethyl acetate in needles, m. p. 175°. [Found: Br, 23.2; S, 9.3. Calc.: Br, 23.1; S, 9.2 per cent.]. This bromophenyltetrahydrothiazole was also prepared by heating

a mixture of *s*-phenyl-*p*-bromophenylthiocarbamide (6.5 g.), monochloroacetic acid (2 g.) and pyridine (2 c. c.) in alcohol for 3 hours. A mixture of both specimens melted at 175°, but admixture with diphenyl-ψ-thiohydantoin (m. p. 175°) caused a depression of 20 to 25°.

(ii) *Synthesis from 2-phenylimino-3-p-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole*.—Bromine (1.4 c. c.) was added to a solution of 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole (0.7 g.) and hydrogen bromide (0.3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 c. c.), when the hydropentabromide crystallised in shining red plates, m. p. 159-60° (decomp. after losing bromine at 145°) after being rapidly dried on porous earthenware in a vacuum [Found: Br (total), 64.1; Br (labile), 42.8 per cent.]. Curiously enough, this specimen of the hydropentabromide appeared to be more stable to the atmosphere than the specimens prepared by direct bromination (compare Hunter, *loc. cit.*).

(iii) *The action of mercuric oxide*.—Precipitated mercuric oxide, dried at 110°, was added with shaking to a solution of the hydropentabromide in chloroform until decolorisation appeared to be complete. The filtered solution was evaporated and the product was recrystallised from alcohol (animal charcoal) when 2-phenylimino-3-*p*-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole was obtained and identified by m. p. and mixed m. p. determination.

(iv) *Thermal dissociation*.—5 G. of freshly prepared hydropentabromide were placed in a dry flask, fitted with a stop-cock, and in series with a soda lime tower, manometer, and an oil pump. The flask was exhausted to 24 mm., placed in an oil-bath at 135-37° and heated for 6 minutes when bromine was copiously evolved with the production of a yellow granular residue consisting of the stable hydrotribromide, which was identified by its properties and also by analysis (Found: Br, 53.8 per cent.).

2-Phenylimino-3-p-bromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole octabromide.—A solution of the *p*-bromophenyltetrahydrothiazole (0.5 g.) in chloroform (3 c. c.) was cooled to 0° and treated with bromine (0.7 c. c. in 0.5 c. c. of chloroform) when the octabromide crystallised in glistening red plates, which were dried on porous earthenware *in vacuo* for 5 minutes and immediately analysed with the precautions used for highly unstable compounds of this type (Dyson, Hunter and Soyoka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 460), m. p. 161-62°. [Found: Br (total), 72.3; Br (labile), 45.2. $C_{15}H_{11}ON_2Br_8$, Br_8 requires Br (total),

72.9 ; Br (labile), 62.5 per cent.]. This compound was also obtained by treating a solution of the bromophenyl derivative (0.5 g.) in chloroform (6 c. c.) with bromine (0.6 c. c. in 0.6 c. c. of chloroform). On reduction with sulphurous acid, or on shaking a chloroform solution of the bromide with mercuric oxide the original *p*-bromophenyltetrahydrothiazole was obtained unaccompanied by other products.

Titration and hydrolysis experiments.—(i) A solution of the octabromide in chloroform (50 c. c.) was treated with excess of aqueous potassium iodide and the mixture was decolorised with sodium thiosulphate solution and the chloroform layer was separated, well washed with distilled water, and evaporated on a water-bath. On recrystallisation from alcohol, *2-phenylimino-3-o-p-dibromophenyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole* was obtained, m.p. 119-20°, which melted at 120° when mixed with the specimen obtained by hydrolysis of the octabromide. (ii) A solution of the octabromide in chloroform (50 c. c.) was shaken with water (20 c. c.) at intervals during a period of 5 minutes and the mixture was thereafter treated with excess of sulphur dioxide. Evaporation of the chloroform layer yielded the *dibromo* derivative which separated from alcohol in small needles, m.p. 121°. (Found: Br, 37.2. $C_{15}H_{10}ON_2Br_2S$ requires Br, 37.5 per cent.).

2-o-Tolylimino-3-p(?)-bromo-o-tolyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole hydroheptabromide.—A solution of di-*o*-tolyl- ψ -thiohydantoin (0.5 g.) (Pozzi Escot, *Compt. rend.*, 1904, 139, 1032) in chloroform (5 c. c.) was treated with bromine (0.7 c. c.), when the hydroheptabromide crystallised after a short time. The bromo-addition compound formed unstable red glistening needles which were collected on a porous earthenware, rapidly dried in high vacuum, and immediately analysed, m.p. 120-21° (decomp.). [Found: Br (total), 69.3; Br (labile), 49.7. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2Br_8$. $HBr(Br_6)$ requires Br (total), 68.4; Br (labile), 51.3 per cent.]. This experiment is typical of a number, and the appreciably high figure for total bromine is due to the same difficulty as that encountered in dealing with other unstable high perbromides of this type which are too unstable to permit crushing of the crystals and redrying in *vacuo* for removal of the last traces of occluded halogen (compare Dyson, Hunter, and Soyka, *loc. cit.*; Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 139). Experiments which have been made in this connection on stable hydrotribromides, such as those of 5:4'-dichloro-1-anilinobenzthiazole and 1-imino-2-ethyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole indicate that the error introduced in

this way is of the order of that observed in the analysis of this hydroheptabromide. On reduction with sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide, the hydroheptabromide yielded 2-*o*-tolylimino-3-*p*(?)-*o*-tolyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole which had m.p. 129° after recrystallisation from alcohol-ethyl acetate. (Found: Br, 27·4. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2BrS$ requires Br, 27·0 per cent.). This was also obtained (m.p. 126°) by evaporation of the chloroform layers obtained in titration experiments on the hydroheptabromide.

On exposure to air, the hydroheptabromide rapidly lost bromine yielding a bright yellow crystalline *hydrotribromide*, m.p. 132° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 51·6. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2Br_4S$ requires Br, 52·0 per cent.).

On more than one occasion in our earlier experiments we isolated a red crystalline bromo-addition compound from the bromination of di-*o*-tolyl- ψ -thiohydantoin which had the composition of a hypopentabromide of 2-*o*-tolylimino-3-bromo-*o*-tolyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole, m.p. 109-10°. (Found: Br, 61·1. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2Br_6S$ requires Br, 61·8 per cent.). The low melting point of this substance suggests, however, that it was most probably a eutectic mixture of the hydroheptabromide and hydrotribromide.

s-o-Tolyl-*p*-bromo-*o*-tolylthiocarbamide.—A solution of *o*-tolylthiocarbimide (1·2 c.c. in 4 c.c. of alcohol) was added to a solution of *p*-bromo-*o*-toluidine (2·5 g.) in the same solvent (8 c.c.), and the mixture was evaporated on a steam-bath until crystallisation commenced. On recrystallisation from alcohol-ethyl acetate (animal charcoal), the *thiocarbamide* was obtained in soft flaky white crystals, m.p. 152°. (Found: Br, 24·3. $C_{15}H_{15}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 23·9 per cent.). Attempts to synthesise 2-*o*-tolylimino-3-*p*-bromo-*o*-tolyl-4-ketotetrahydrothiazole from this compound by condensation with monochloroacetic acid and pyridine in alcohol led only to gummy resins which could not be investigated.

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